

THE EFFECT OF SCAPULOTHORACIC ELLIPSOID JOINT PARAMETERS ON MARKER TRACKING ERRORS

Eva Herbst(1,2), Stephen J. Ferguson(1), Philipp Moroder(2)

1. ETH Zürich, Switzerland; 2. Schulthess Klinik, Switzerland

Introduction

The scapulothoracic (ST) joint is often modeled as a contact of the scapula on an ellipsoid. For kinematic analysis of motion data, no ST joint is needed. However, when driving a simulation model with motion data, the ST joint stabilizes the simulation and provides more realistic muscle activity estimates by limiting scapular movement against the thorax. The ST joint developed by [1] in OpenSim is a four degree of freedom joint enabling scapular elevation, abduction, upward rotation, and winging. The ellipsoid center, radii, and orientation, the scapular contact point, and the scapular (child) joint frame can be adjusted. ST ellipsoids have been defined either by static markers (i.e. scaling existing ST to subject) [2] or fitted to minimize marker error [1]. Scapular kinematics are sensitive to changes in ellipsoid radii and center [2,3]. Further investigations are warranted to test ST joint parameter fitting. We developed and compared methods for determining the scapular joint frame and for fitting an ellipsoid to static and dynamic marker data. Marker tracking errors were quantified against biplane fluoroscopy data.

Methods

We implemented the OpenSim ellipsoid ST joint[1] in ArtiSynth (www.artisynth.org). Biplane fluoroscopy data [4] was transformed to analyse scapular motion relative to the thorax during coronal plane abduction. For ellipsoid A, 9 markers were chosen on the anterior scapular blade of the patient-specific scapula in the resting pose (Fig. 1A). For ellipsoid B, the angulus inferior (ai) and scapular contact point were traced throughout the motion and these traces were used to fit the ellipsoid. For both models, an ellipsoid was fit to scapular markers (duplicated and mirrored across the midline) and the thorax centerpoint in Python. A point in the middle of the scapular blade was used as the scapular contact point and scapular joint frame origin. To assess the effect of the scapular joint frame, 3 ST joints were created for ellipsoid A with 3 different scapular joint frames: A1) scapular joint frame formed by rotating the International Society of Biomechanics scapular frame -90 degrees about Y, A2) A1 adjusted by aligning the Z axis to the normal vector of a plane fit to ts (trigonum spinae), ai, and a marker on the lateral scapular blade, and A3) A1 adjusted to align the Z axis to the normal vector of the plane tangent to the ellipsoid at the scapular contact point. The scapular joint frame with lowest marker error was used for the comparison between ellipsoids A and B. Euclidean distances of ts, ai, and aa (angulus acromialis) markers between ST models were used to quantify the error of the ST joint.

Results

Of the 3 methods of defining the scapular joint frame, A3 performed the best (Table 1), and ellipsoid B (based on dynamic markers) performed better than ellipsoid A (based on static markers) (Table 1, Figure 1).

Figure 1: A) Ellipsoid A, fit to static markers; B) ST joint A1; C) ST joint A3. Tracking of model markers (blue) compared to biplane (red). D) Marker tracking errors.

Marker	A1	A2	A3	B
ts	11.8 (2.9)	13.1 (2.9)	6.3 (2.8)	3.6 (2.0)
aa	2.2 (0.6)	2.4 (0.6)	1.9 (0.7)	1.3 (0.7)
ai	16.7 (5.4)	18.5 (5.4)	8.8 (5.1)	1.9 (1.2)

Table 1: RMSE (error = Euclidean distance from biplane markers in mm). SD in parentheses.

Discussion

Here, we demonstrate good marker tracking error using both A3 (static) and B (dynamic) based ellipsoids, and identified a promising method to calculate the scapular joint frame. Defining the ST ellipsoid with static markers is useful in cases of noisy marker data, or to include patient specific posture and anatomy when a resting pose (i.e. through upright CT) is available but generic motion data is used to drive the model.

References

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Acknowledgements

We thank John Lloyd and Ian Stavness for Artisynth development, and the Schwyzer Stiftung for funding.

